

MODERN REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DESIGN OF EARTHQUAKE-RESISTANT BUILDINGS

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Abstract. This research paper provides ways to optimize design solutions for architectural and space-planning solutions for earthquake-resistant buildings.

Keywords: earthquake resistance of buildings, seismic protection methods, seismic isolators, special method.

Introduction.

Nowadays, specialists from Uzbekistan and foreign countries have proposed a variety of devices for seismic isolation systems and vibration dampers of structures, as well as systems using alloys that store the volumetric state and other intelligent systems.

The following trends are observed in the world: the first is the use of seismic isolation of buildings in its pure form, which is usually arranged in the lower floors: rubber-metal supports of various modifications, with low and high damping, with and without a lead core, using various materials. There are also pendulum-type friction sliding bearings, and those other bearings are used very widely in the world.

Methods of research.

The second direction is the use of damping (oscillation damping), which has been known for a very long time and is constantly being improved. For high-rise construction, as a rule, a combination is used: seismic isolation is located in the lower floor, and damping is installed along the height of the building. Now manufacturers offer a variety of dampers: metal, liquid, there are special alloys with memory, special damping walls, the latest devices, although relatively expensive, are quite effective.

It is possible to significantly reduce the horizontal loads transmitted to the load-bearing above-ground structures of the building, if they are allowed to slip relative to the foundation. Part of the energy imparted to the structure is spent in this

case not on overcoming the resistance of bonds in the structure, but on overcoming the forces of sliding friction. The sliding belt is a series of supports with plates made of materials with a low coefficient of sliding friction. It is arranged between the supporting structures of the building and the foundation or directly in the foundation, cutting it in a horizontal plane. Pendulum seismic isolators can be a striking example of such devices. This device works on the functional principle of a pendulum. It allows the structure to swing freely in a horizontal plane in the event of an earthquake, while seismic energy is dissipated due to friction between sliding surfaces. The curved sliding surface of the balancers returns the structure to its original position under the influence of gravity.

Isolators reliably provide the following main functions:

- In normal operation, they transmit vertical loads and allow horizontal movements
- Under seismic action, they provide structural flexibility in the horizontal plane due to the sliding of the main element along the initially curved surface (fig.2).
- Provide energy dissipation through dynamic friction between stainless steel sliding surface and high quality sliding material
- The design of the device, combined with the force of gravity, ensures the return of the structure to a central position.

Fig.1. Seismic isolators

Seismic isolation consists in separating the structure during an earthquake from the movements of the base, which could damage it. For this, special insulator devices are installed in certain places of the structure, allowing it to work properly during an earthquake.

Conclusion.

Consequently, seismic isolation devices provide the necessary design flexibility in order to achieve the maximum possible difference between the natural oscillation period of the structure and the earthquake period. This prevents the occurrence of resonance, which can lead to damage or even collapse of the structure.

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